

YOUNG FAMILY CONCEPT, ESSENCE AND ITS DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERISTICS

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Annotation. The article highlights the reforms carried out in the country, the influence of the family on the upbringing of a spiritually mature, physically healthy generation, the harmony of their upbringing with universal human values, the inviolability of the family and marriage, ensuring the stability of families through instilling the sanctity of the family and marriage in the minds of the younger generation.

Key words: reform, family, values, marriage, healthy environment, harmoniously developed generation, society, nation.

Any change in the life of the country, the implemented reforms, are first of all reflected in families. Therefore, ensuring peace and tranquility in families, healthy environment and moderation is one of the most important tasks before us. After all, a harmonious and strong family is the support of the country, its reliable future, the center of kindness and spirituality that raises the honor of the nation to the highest. After all, if our families are peaceful, our society will be peaceful and prosperous, and our children will grow up in a full spiritual and spiritual environment.

Our main goal is to preserve the rich and meaningful national traditions related to the family, to harmonize them with universal values, to preserve the sanctity of the family and marriage, taking into account the important role of the family in the development of society, raising a spiritually mature and physically healthy generation. consists of scientific study of ensuring the stability of families by instilling them deeply into the minds of the young generation. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 2, 2018 No. PF-5325 "On

measures to fundamentally improve activities in the field of supporting women and girls and strengthening the family institution" and dated June 27, 2018 In accordance with the Decision No. PQ-3808 "On approval of the concept of strengthening the institution of the family in the Republic of Uzbekistan", a new stage in the state policy focused on the family, its stability, happiness and well-being was defined. The family is considered a small part of the foundation of the state, and it is a unique barometer of all reforms in society. From this point of view, the family determines the priorities of development of the economy, social sphere, culture and, in general, society. If we pay attention to the chronology, 1998 is the "Year of the Family" in Uzbekistan, and the following years are respectively "Year of Women", "Year of Healthy Generation", "Year of Mother and Child", "Year of Health". , "The Year of Youth", "The Year of the Perfect Generation", "The Year of the Strong Family", "The Year of the Healthy Child", "The Year of the Healthy Mother and Child" and the current year as "The Year of Youth Support and Public Health Promotion" was announced.

It is worth noting that the State program covering all aspects of family life, in particular economic, social, cultural, pedagogical, legal and other factors, was developed for each year. State institutions and organizations, women's and youth organizations, the general public, as well as our entire nation actively participated in the implementation of these programs. At the same time, a large-scale policy and reforms on social protection of the population were implemented in the republic, in which, of course, the family was put in the first place. Family is a small social group bound by moral responsibility, mutual respect, understanding and affection based on marriage and close kinship. If we give a direct legal assessment to a young family, a young family is a family in which both spouses are under the age of thirty. It should be said that the young family is at the stage of forming new relationships (interpersonal and intra-family), new status (rights of the bride, young family), new economic situation (financial support of the young family, personal financial resources), new life directions. . According to the results

of many studies conducted by scientists, it has been confirmed that the stability of a young family in the formation of new status and relationships is mainly related to the readiness of young people for family life.

Approaches to raising a child are formed depending on how family relationships are built, and the distribution of roles in the middle. In addition to the implementation of measures aimed at morally and materially supporting young families in our country, improving their housing and living conditions, involving them in business activities, as well as raising their level of knowledge new works are being carried out, innovative schools are being created to prepare future young men and women for family life. Despite the reforms aimed at comprehensive support for young families, there are a number of shortcomings in this regard, which should be thoroughly studied and positively resolved. First of all, preparing the growing generation for family life is considered an urgent issue. In this regard, it is necessary to carry out effective activities in a number of directions in order to prepare young people for family life.

Firstly, in the spiritual and moral direction, young people have spiritual and moral values, including respect for parents, elders and children, child upbringing; responsibility, loyalty, honesty; patriotism and a sense of duty to one's wife (spouse), family, children and, in general, society, it is necessary to teach the manners of sexual intimacy.

Secondly, it is important to comprehensively explain the social aspects of the family, that is, the essence of marriage and family relations, the role of the family in society, the essence of the social functions of spouses and parents.

Thirdly, attention should be paid to psychological aspects. In this regard, it is considered appropriate to develop the characteristics of the psychology of relations between men and women, spouses, parents and children, emotions necessary for marriage and family life, and communication skills. .

Fourth, to know the basics of marriage and family law in the legal direction; it is necessary to know and master the obligations related to the relationship of the spouses to each other, to their children and to the society.

Fifth, in young families, it is important to form pedagogical aspects - the pedagogical potential of parents, their educational tasks, and raising the pedagogical culture of parents.

Sixth, by strengthening economic and economic aspects, that is, family budget, lifestyle culture, household management skills and knowledge, adaptation to large family life is easier in young families.

Seventh, it is necessary to pay attention to the physical and reproductive health of young people (future bride and groom).

The importance of sexual and moral education plays an important role in preparing young people for family life. The main task of sex education is to prepare young people for family life, to promote a healthy lifestyle, to equip young people with physiological, medical, socio-spiritual, and spiritual knowledge and skills similar to their gender. forming, ensuring that the young generation reaches a healthy age, having reproductive (begetting) abilities, and helping to strengthen marriage and family. Sexual education aims to establish the correct attitude towards male-female relations and gender issues in boys and girls. Sexual education should be carried out in harmony with spiritual-ethical, physical, mental-intellectual, aesthetic education, it should start in the family, it should be carried out in cooperation with parents, doctors, pedagogues, it should be consistent with the child's age, gender and other characteristics. needed.

After all, education is not limited to introducing the basics of sexual life, explaining to children hygienic skills, the structure of the male and female body, the stages and laws of sexual development, but also inculcating the correct attitude towards gender, the unique characteristics of boys and girls. attention to education, gender equality, distance between children in interaction, sensitive concepts of gender, age-appropriate communication of issues related to marriage and marriage,

permission and prohibitions in this regard, and the difference between halal and haram. includes It is desirable to teach young people the real purpose of family building, the necessity of sexual life, and its rules in a unique way, using modern medical and health knowledge in accordance with mental characteristics, instructions of our religion and national traditions.

In some families, parents are indifferent to sex education or refuse to talk about it, as a result, after the children get married, various problems, conflicts and disagreements arise because of these issues. Our forefathers, the children of the family, distinguish between halal and haram

They have supported the methods of sexual education so that they become moral owners who fight for their honor and pride, and for boys to grow up to be honorable and girls to be chaste and dreamy. By effectively conveying to young men and women from adolescence the secrets of family life, conjugal etiquette, respect for representatives of the opposite sex, and the knowledge of giving birth and raising a child.

the basis for the stability of a young family is created. Religious values, which are the spiritual foundation of the Uzbek family, occupy an important place. In fiqh books, topics related to sexual thinking (family building, marriage, conjugal etiquette, menstruation, bleeding during childbirth, pregnancy, giving birth) are explained in detail. "According to the teaching of Islam, the family is created in order to find the approval of the Creator, to be adorned with the morals of our Prophet (pbuh), to be adorned with Islamic manners, and to continue the human race in a pure way. Therefore, our religion attaches great importance to building a family based on marriage and highly values marriage as the most important human relationship. The peace and prosperity of the society, free from all kinds of evil and corruption, depends first of all on the peace of this small society." It should be noted separately that the strength of the young family, the stability of the spiritual environment in it, the observance of the health and healthy lifestyle of young people and the fact that they have the skills in this regard also depends.

There are five main conditions for a healthy lifestyle, and these are, first of all, proper nutrition, physical activity, avoidance of harmful habits, proper organization of work and active rest, and adherence to hygienic skills. . It should be noted with special responsibility that the development of young families, which are the foundation of our country, and the health of the foundations of our future, must start with the family first of all. According to scientists, 51.6% of human health depends on a healthy lifestyle, 20.5% on heredity, 19.3% on the external environment, and 8.6% on the health care system. It is also known that health is directly related to how each person lives, what he eats, who he deals with, and how he can properly organize a suitable and comfortable lifestyle for himself both at work and at rest. it is. Today, there is a lot of attention around the world on health and a healthy lifestyle. For example, American scientists are more likely to associate them with aggressive behavior when asked what causes them to look behind their paws. That is, a person becomes belligerent, irritable, and impatient. This ultimately leads to drug addiction, alcoholism, unhealthy relationships between husband and wife in the family, increased prejudice against women, indifference to sports, and interpersonal conflicts.

The importance of an all-round healthy family environment in raising a perfect generation is incomparable. After all, a healthy family is the basis of a healthy society, the foundation of the owners of tomorrow. When it comes to the characteristics of young families,

one should not forget the family in general. After all, the "big family" is at the base of family values, at its foundation, that is, grandparents, parents, children and other forms of family relations. Looking at world practice, the family model is divided into three main types: traditional, modern and post-Soviet (innovative) family. These models may operate in parallel, but have a clear historical sequence. In this case, in the "Traditional Family Model" the roles of men and women are clearly divided and attached. A man is the head of the family with financial resources and the main decision-maker. In this regard, there is a combination of

roles within the family. A woman is subordinate to a man, she is engaged in housework and raising children. Children, in turn, obey their parents, the influence of any family member depends on his gender and age.

Family values are the basis for "parent-child" relations. In the "modern family model", the increase in the political, economic and social status of women leads to a change in family roles and norms of family life. A parent balances professional career and family responsibilities. As for the "innovative family model" (families of the post-Soviet space), this type of family is in harmony with the prospects for the development of society and the requirements of the world economy. This is, on the one hand, the intergenerational circulation of basic cultural values and attitudes, and on the other hand, attention is paid to the manifestation of family problems in a global rather than individual way, as well as the formation of a well-rounded personality, capable of creating and implementing innovative ideas. implies the responsibility of increasing the number of young people. Currently, scientists distinguish between traditional and modern family types. The form characteristic of our people is the traditional family, which is a multi-generational family built on the basis of mutual respect and solidarity, characterized by the high prestige of the head of the family, valuing the elderly and caring for the children. According to the results of surveys conducted in families, it became known that there is a family model in Uzbekistan characterized by a specific hierarchy among family members, that is, the distribution of functions and tasks of family members. That is, there is a leader in the family - the head of the family, who is responsible for the order in the house and the responsibilities of the family members, who is considered to be the guarantee of resolving disputes and managing the family budget. According to the results of such surveys, it became known that men have certain obligations to family members. In particular, these include material well-being (90 percent of respondents) and satisfactory living conditions (47 percent), creating opportunities for children to get an education (22 percent), participation in raising children (34 percent). A woman's responsibilities

include raising children (64 percent) and taking care of them (55 percent), running a household (50 percent), and responsibility for a comfortable psychological environment in the family (30 percent). At the same time, mutual understanding, respect and patience (61 percent), material well-being (28 percent) and others should be present in order to establish strong relationships in the family.

In conclusion, it should be noted that young families have their own characteristics, and ensuring their positive balance and harmony serves the strength of the family. Also, according to scientists, the time required for a young family to strengthen and stand on its feet, to independently solve various household problems, actually depends on the sincere relationship of two married people to each other, different values of the family and its surroundings. It directly depends on their relatively harmonious views, on their ability to apply what they saw as an example in their parents' family in their own family. However, every family experiences certain difficulties during their youth, which manifest themselves in the following main circumstances: - lack of time to ensure family life, work, study or solve other issues ;

- having a good time, limited entertainment;
- physical exhaustion, nervous exhaustion of both men and women in new conditions;
- economic difficulties.

On the one hand, the last situation is explained by the increase of dreams and desires among young people, on the other hand, it is closely related to the growth of spending related to the dreams and desires of parents.

In modern Uzbekistan, our life and living conditions are improving day by day, despite the fact that there are sufficient conditions for the well-being of the family, from the outside, it seems that something is missing even in a young family that has solved all its household problems. These, in turn, are those dreams and desires, social explained by the ever-increasing needs. At the same time, young

families face educational, spiritual, psychological, material, economic, and social problems.

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